

Adjoint Optimization of Turbomachinery Components Under Mechanical Constraints

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Abstract

This paper summarizes work done within the framework of an adjoint multidisciplinary optimization for turbomachinery components. Adjoint models for the linear stress and vibration analysis are implemented by the discrete adjoint method using algorithmic differentiation. It is also shown that the design space of the implemented adjoint models can be extended to compute sensitivities relevant to composite material applications.

Keywords: adjoints, algorithmic differentiation, linear stress analysis, vibration analysis, composite materials, turbomachinery

1. Introduction

In the field of turbomachinery, state of the art adjoint optimization methods focus on aerodynamic cost functions and constraints [1; 2; 3]. Structural constraints are often considered *a posteriori* rather than within the optimization. As a result, the optimized shape may be aerodynamically optimized, but structurally infeasible. This can lead to expensive design re-iterations. To avoid this, an adjoint multidisciplinary optimization (MDO) framework is required that can converge towards aerodynamically optimal designs that obey the structural constraints. An adjoint implementation within such a framework is discussed in section 2.

Structural constraints of prime importance in the design of turbomachinery components are stress and vibration. Centrifugal forces caused by high rotational speeds lead to significant stresses and deformations, while the unsteady pressure forces from the surrounding fluid can cause unwanted

vibrations. Taking these effects into account within a structurally constrained optimization is paramount. This project works with the VKI's in-house MDO framework *CADO* [4]. Previous work within this PhD project involves the implementation of an adjoint cold-to-hot CAD deformation for this framework [5]. This deforms the CAD geometry based on the structural deformations caused mainly by centrifugal forces. An adjoint structural solver for stress and vibration analysis is required to include the structural constraints within an adjoint MDO. These are discussed in sections 3 and 4, respectively.

Composite material applications are gaining more traction in turbomachinery due to their light weight and customizable material properties. The structural solver described in this paper is extended to offer the capability of composite material vibration analysis. Here an extended design space is used to evaluate sensitivities with respect to composite material properties as well, enabling simultaneous material optimizations

in addition to traditional shape optimizations. This is explored in section 5.

2. Adjoint Multidisciplinary Optimization

Multidisciplinary optimization methods seek to converge towards an optimal design that adheres to cost and constraint functions from multiple domains, e.g. fluid and structure. For turbomachinery applications, this is of great importance, as most components experience high centrifugal forces and unsteady pressure loads. Optimization methods used to achieve this goal can be classified into two categories: gradient-free and gradient-based methods.

Gradient-free optimization methods are widely used and have been successfully applied in turbomachinery applications [6; 7]. Due to their non-intrusive nature requiring only function evaluations, they are relatively straightforward to implement and can be used to work with codes that are treated as a *black box*. Unfortunately, these methods suffer from the curse of dimensionality. The cost of performing a gradient-free optimization is proportional to the number of design parameters m , which can be significantly large. Additionally, a high amount of iterations is typically required to converge towards an optimum.

On the other hand, gradient-based optimization methods use the gradients of the cost function $\sigma \in \mathbb{R}$ with respect to the design $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^m$

$$\frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \in \mathbb{R}^m \quad (1)$$

to converge towards an optimum with less iterations. Computing the gradient can be an expensive task using methods such as finite differences, where $m + 1$ evaluations of the cost function would be required for a first order approximation. With large design spaces, computing the gradient easily becomes infeasible.

The adjoint method, which was applied in aerodynamic optimization by Pironneau [8] and later by Jameson [9; 10], offers an efficient alternative for computing gradients. The key difference is that gradients can be computed at a cost proportional to the number of outputs n , rather than the number of inputs m . In most turbomachinery optimization problems, the case is usually that the number of design parameters m is far greater than the number of cost functions

and constraints n , such that $n \ll m$. Utilizing this method boils down to deriving an adjoint model of the form

$$\bar{\mathbf{x}} = \frac{\partial \sigma^T}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \bar{\sigma}, \quad (2)$$

where the bar notation $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ is used to define an adjoint variable. The adjoint model is then *seeded* by setting the adjoint of the input $\bar{\sigma} = 1$. Running the adjoint model will result in

$$\bar{\mathbf{x}} = \frac{\partial \sigma^T}{\partial \mathbf{x}}, \quad (3)$$

so that the needed gradient can be extracted from the adjoint variable $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$.

There exist two general approaches for implementing the adjoint model. First, there is the *continuous adjoint* approach [11], which derives an adjoint model from the continuous *primal* equations, e.g. the Navier-Stokes equations. The continuous adjoint model is then discretized to be solved numerically. However, deriving a continuous adjoint model is a meticulous and arduous task. Alternatively, the *discrete adjoint* approach derives an adjoint model from the discretized set of equations. A discrete adjoint model can be derived using the source code transformation method *algorithmic differentiation* (AD), using a procedure referred to as *reverse AD*. A list of different AD tools can be found on the community's webpage www.autodiff.org. In this work, the operator-overloading AD tool CoDiPack [12] is used. The interested reader is referred to [13; 14] for more information on algorithmic differentiation.

AD can also be used to derive the tangent model of a code using the chain rule of differentiation. The tangent model has the form

$$\dot{\sigma} = \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \dot{\mathbf{x}}, \quad (4)$$

where the dot notation $\dot{\mathbf{x}}$ is used to denote a tangent variable. The tangent variable is seeded with a unit vector, which is a vector where all vector components are 0, except the i -th component, which is 1. Seeding

$\dot{\mathbf{x}}$ with the i -th unit vector,

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

and plugging this into the tangent model (4), computes the derivative

$$\dot{\sigma} = \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial x_i}. \quad (6)$$

For m input parameters, m tangent models would have to be run to compute the entire gradient. This method is also referred to as *forward AD* and has a computational cost of $O(m) \cdot \text{cost}(F)$, where $\text{cost}(F)$ denotes the cost of evaluating the primal function. Big O notation is used to describe that the cost of computing the gradient is

$$\text{cost}(\text{gradient}) \leq c \cdot m \cdot \text{cost}(F), \quad c \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (7)$$

where usually the constant $c \in [2, 2.5]$ for forward AD, depending on the platform. Reverse AD would compute the same gradient at a cost of $O(n) \cdot \text{cost}(F)$, i.e. $O(1) \cdot \text{cost}(F)$, since the number of outputs $n = 1$ in this example. For reverse AD, the constant c is expected to be within the range $c \in [3, 4]$. From a computational effort point of view, the main difference is that the cost of computing a gradient using the tangent method is proportional to the number of inputs m , while the cost of using the adjoint method is proportional to the number of outputs n .

While AD can be applied on a structural solver in a black-box fashion, two important components must be treated manually - the iterative linear solver for the linear stress analysis and the iterative eigenvalue solver for the vibration analysis. Failure to do so could lead to incorrect gradients, higher memory requirements, and longer run times. This treatment is discussed in sections 3 and 4, respectively.

3. Adjoint Linear Stress Analysis

The governing equations of a linear stress analysis is a linear system of equations of the form

$$A\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{b}, \quad (8)$$

where $A \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ is the stiffness matrix, $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ the vector of displacements, and $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ the load vector [15]. The stiffness matrix A and the load vector \mathbf{b} are computed from the material properties and boundary conditions, such as fixed nodes, point loads, or distributed loads. Turbomachinery applications typically apply centrifugal loads.

For the structural constraints, the maximum von Mises stress $\sigma_{max}(\mathbf{u}) \in \mathbb{R}$ is considered. In order to be able to differentiate the constraint function, the maximum von Mises stress is determined using a continuous function, such as the p -norm or the Kreisselmeier-Steinhauser function [16].

Table 1: Linear stress analysis chain of operations

Step	Input	Description	Output
1	\mathbf{x}	Linear system assembly	A, \mathbf{b}
2	A, \mathbf{b}	Linear system solve	\mathbf{u}
3	\mathbf{u}	Cost function evaluation	σ_{max}

Table 2: Adjoint linear stress analysis chain of operations

Step	Input	Description	Output
1	$\bar{\sigma}_{max}$	Cost function evaluation	$\bar{\mathbf{u}}$
2	$\bar{\mathbf{u}}$	Linear system solve	$\bar{A}, \bar{\mathbf{b}}$
3	$\bar{A}, \bar{\mathbf{b}}$	Linear system assembly	$\bar{\mathbf{x}}$

For design variables $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^m$, the gradient

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_{max}}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \in \mathbb{R}^m \quad (9)$$

is required to take stress constraints into consideration in a gradient-based optimization. Using the design variables \mathbf{x} as an input, the structural solver's chain of operations can be listed as in table 1. First, the stiffness matrix A and the load vector \mathbf{b} are computed in the assembly phase to set up the linear system (8). The linear system is then solved for the displacements \mathbf{u} , which are used to evaluate the cost function, e.g. the maximum von Mises stress σ_{max} . The reverse order gives us the adjoint chain of operations of table 2, which would be seeded with $\bar{\sigma}_{max} = 1$. The resulting gradient is then given by the adjoint variable

$$\bar{\mathbf{x}} = \frac{\partial \sigma_{max}}{\partial \mathbf{x}}^T. \quad (10)$$

While the linear system assembly and the cost function evaluation within this chain of operations can be easily differentiated using AD, the linear system solve, which usually consists of an iterative solver, requires special treatment. Differentiating an iterative linear solver using a black-box approach means that its adjoint would use the same number of iterations and the same Krylov subspace. This may lead to wrong results, which will propagate through the adjoint model. As described in [17], the adjoint model of a linear solver can be treated in such a way that its resulting adjoint variables can be computed as

$$\bar{\mathbf{b}} = A^{-T} \bar{\mathbf{u}}, \quad \bar{A}_{i,j} = -u_j \bar{b}_i. \quad (11)$$

Due to the symmetric positive definite properties of the stiffness matrix A , this can be further simplified to a linear system

$$A \bar{\mathbf{b}} = \bar{\mathbf{u}}, \quad (12)$$

where the same stiffness matrix A of the primal problem can be recycled. The resulting adjoint variables $\bar{\mathbf{b}}$ and \bar{A} can then be plugged into the algorithmically differentiated cost function to compute $\bar{\sigma}_{max}$, which will contain the gradient (9).

3.1. Gradient Accuracy and Runtime Comparison

The gradient (9) computed using the adjoint method is validated by comparing it with the gradient computed using finite differences and forward AD. As an accuracy test case, a rotating cantilever beam with $m = 270$ degrees of freedom (figure 1) is used. As is shown in figure 2, the gradient computed using the adjoint method matches the gradients computed using forward AD and finite differences.

Figure 1: Rotating cantilever beam test case

Runtime tests were done using an axial fan geometry [18] with approximately $m \approx 200,000$ degrees of freedom, which is shown in figure 3. The time

Figure 2: Maximum von Mises stress sensitivity $|\frac{\partial \sigma_{max}}{\partial x}|$. Comparison of adjoint vs forward AD vs FD

taken to compute the entire gradient (9) is measured. As a reference, the time it takes to complete one cost function evaluation T and the memory required M is measured as well. Using finite differences or forward AD, e.g., it is estimated that computing the gradient would cost approximately $m \cdot T$. Using the adjoint method, we are able to compute the gradient at a relative cost of $2.1 \cdot T$ with a relative memory requirement of $6.4 \cdot M$. The sensitivities (9) are visualized in figure 4.

Figure 3: Rotating axial fan test case

Figure 4: Maximum von Mises stress sensitivities $|\frac{\partial \sigma_{max}}{\partial \mathbf{x}}|$

4. Adjoint Vibration Analysis

A free vibration analysis takes the form a generalized eigenvalue problem

$$(A - \lambda_k B) \mathbf{u}_k = 0, \quad (13)$$

where B is the mass matrix, λ_k is the k -th eigenfrequency, \mathbf{u}_k is the k -th eigenvector, and A is the same stiffness matrix used in the stress analysis. An iterative eigenvalue solver can be used to solve this system.

Applying vibrational constraints within a gradient-based optimization requires the gradients of the eigenfrequencies with respect to the design variables

$$\frac{\partial \lambda_k}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \in \mathbb{R}^m, \quad k = 0, \dots, p - 1, \quad (14)$$

where p denotes the number of eigenfrequencies computed. Starting with the design variables \mathbf{x} as our input, the chain of operations can be enumerated as in table 3. First, the stiffness and mass matrices A , B are computed. These are then used to set up the generalized eigenvalue problem of (13), which is solved for the k -th eigenfrequency λ_k and eigenmode \mathbf{u}_k . For the vibration constraint, we are only interested in the eigenfrequency sensitivities. Again, the adjoint model goes in the reverse direction as in table 4. Seeding the adjoint model with $\bar{\lambda}_k = 1$, would give us the sensitivities of the k -th eigenvalue from the adjoint variable

$$\bar{\mathbf{x}} = \frac{\partial \lambda_k}{\partial \mathbf{x}}^T. \quad (15)$$

Table 3: Vibration analysis chain of operations

Step	Input	Description	Output
1	$\bar{\mathbf{x}}$	Assembly	A, B
2	A, B	Generalized eigenvalue solve	λ_k

Table 4: Adjoint vibration analysis chain of operations

Step	Input	Description	Output
1	$\bar{\lambda}_k$	Generalized eigenvalue solve	\bar{A}, \bar{B}
2	\bar{A}, \bar{B}	Assembly	$\bar{\mathbf{x}}$

Similarly to the manual treatment of the iterative linear solver in section 3, the adjoint model of the iterative solver for the generalized eigenvalue solver can be derived as:

$$\bar{A}_{i,j} = \bar{\lambda}_k u_{k,i} u_{k,j} \quad (16)$$

$$\bar{B}_{i,j} = -\bar{\lambda}_k \lambda_k u_{k,i} u_{k,j} \quad (17)$$

An adjoint generalized eigenvalue solve is thus replaced by (16) and (17), cutting the gradient evaluation costs significantly. The resulting adjoint variables \bar{A} and \bar{B} are then plugged into the adjoint mass and stiffness matrix assemblies, which are differentiated using AD. Note that the stiffness matrix assembly from the linear stress analysis can be recycled here.

4.1. Gradient Accuracy and Runtime Comparison

The same gradient accuracy test case used in section 3.1 is used to validate the vibration analysis gradients. The gradients (14) are computed using the adjoint method, finite differences, and forward AD. Comparisons for the 2nd and 5th eigenvalues are shown in figures 5 and 6. The gradients computed using the adjoint method match the gradients computed using finite differences and forward AD.

Similar runtime measurements are done using the axial fan geometry of section 3.1. Since the stiffness matrix A can be recycled from the linear stress analysis, its assembly is not considered in the time measurements. The adjoint vibration evaluations are significantly cheap compared to the forward vibration evaluations. Performing $p = 10$ adjoint

Figure 5: Eigenfrequency sensitivity $|\frac{\partial \lambda_1}{\partial x}|$. Comparison of adjoint vs forward AD vs FD

Figure 6: Eigenfrequency sensitivity $|\frac{\partial \lambda_4}{\partial x}|$. Comparison of adjoint vs forward AD vs FD

evaluations to compute the the sensitivities (14) for 10 eigenfrequencies, costs only $\approx 11\%$ of the runtime of a single forward evaluation. This is mainly due to the fact that the eigenvalue solver, which makes up the majority of the runtime (99.5%), has been taken out of the adjoint model and replaced by direct evaluations (16) and (17). The gradient results for the second eigenfrequency λ_1 are shown in figure 7.

5. Extension to Composite Shell Elements

The structural solver's program structure, and in particular its discrete adjoint, is generalized to allow the definition of different functions for the evaluation of matrices A and B , inputs x , and cost function σ . This is particularly interesting when exploring more specific structural problems. For instance, isotropic

Figure 7: Eigenfrequency sensitivities $|\frac{\partial \lambda_1}{\partial x}|$

materials have constant material properties and the stiffness and mass matrices A and B are dependent on design variables x , e.g. the node coordinates. The maximum von Mises stress σ_{max} is evaluated as the cost function. In contrast, composite material matrices A and B rely on additional input parameters related to the material's composition. Typically, a cost function, such as the Tsai-Wu criterion $\sigma_{TW} \in \mathbb{R}$, is used to evaluate the composite structural analysis. For a more detailed discussion on composite materials and their optimization methods, the interested reader is referred to [19; 20].

5.1. Integration into Structural Solver Framework

The linear stress analysis (sec. 3), the vibration analysis (sec. 4), and their respective adjoints consist of just a few main building blocks that can be adjusted according to the specific application at hand. These blocks are mainly composed of the following:

- input x
- stiffness matrix A
- mass matrix B
- cost function σ

Each of these building blocks can be defined as separate functions within an element class that can be overridden by derived classes. The results shown in sections 3.1 and 4.1 were achieved using isotropic elements.

Composite element support is achieved by implementing composite-specific definitions and functions for \mathbf{x} , A , B , and σ . This was done by defining isotropic and composite element subclasses that derive from a common element class, as depicted in figure 8. The derived classes then define their own functions for inputs, stiffness matrix, mass matrix, and cost function. By AD'ing the superclass, the differentiation is automatically implemented for the derived classes. As long as the overall structure of the linear stress and vibration analysis does not change, no additional differentiation is required for the subclasses. This showcases the advantages of code extensibility that an operator-overloading AD tool can provide. As the code evolves, developers can focus on the implementation of the primal problem and need to worry less about the differentiation.

Figure 8: Inheritance for element class

5.2. Extension of Design Space

Composite material applications based on first-order shear deformation theory (FSDT) offer additional lamination parameters $V \in \mathbb{R}^l$ as design parameters [21]. Sensitivities with respect to the lamination parameters,

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_{TW}}{\partial V} \in \mathbb{R}^l, \quad (18)$$

could be taken into consideration alongside sensitivities with respect to node coordinates to perform concurrent shape and material optimization. In this sense, the design space can be extended to include lamination parameters:

$$\mathbf{x}^* := (\mathbf{x}, V), \quad \mathbf{x}^* \in \mathbb{R}^{n+l} \quad (19)$$

Accordingly, the dependency of the stiffness and mass matrices changes such that

$$A = A(\mathbf{x}^*), \quad B = B(\mathbf{x}^*). \quad (20)$$

The same adjoint implementations described in sections 3 and 4 can be used to perform a sensitivity anal-

ysis with respect to the extended design space. The resulting sensitivities using the adjoint linear stress analysis and adjoint vibration analysis are

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_{TW}}{\partial \mathbf{x}^*} \in \mathbb{R}^{n+l}, \quad \frac{\partial \lambda_k}{\partial \mathbf{x}^*} \in \mathbb{R}^{n+l}. \quad (21)$$

5.3. Gradient Accuracy

The vibration analysis gradients with respect to the extended design space \mathbf{x}^* computed using the adjoint method, finite differences, and forward AD were compared. The results for the vibration sensitivities with respect to a lamination parameter are shown in figure 9 and the resulting gradients show a good agreement with one another.

Figure 9: Eigenfrequency sensitivities $|\frac{\partial \lambda_0}{\partial V_{11}}|$

6. Conclusion

Discrete adjoint models have been implemented for both the linear stress analysis and the free vibration analysis. Special care is taken to treat the iterative solvers of the linear stress analysis and vibration analysis manually to reduce errors and improve performance. The extensibility of the adjoint structural solver has been demonstrated by extending the design space by additional material design variables used in composite material design. The gradients computed using the adjoint method have an excellent agreement with the gradients computed using finite differences or forward AD.

Future work will bridge the gap between the structural solver's computational mesh and the CAD geometry by the implementation of a discrete adjoint mesh deformation. This will enable the computation of structural sensitivities with respect to CAD design parameters directly. Additionally, the links between the fluid and structure domains, e.g. interpolating pressure forces from the fluid domain onto the structural domain, need to be differentiated as well to support an adjoint fluid-structure interaction problem.

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